

NEAR-JUNCTION MICROFLUIDIC THERMAL MANAGEMENT OF RF POWER AMPLIFIERS

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Abstract — While gallium nitride (GaN) is attracting broad attention as the wide bandgap material of choice for both industrial and defense applications, thermal impediments present a significant barrier to full exploitation of its inherently high electron sheet charge density and electrical breakdown voltage. For the last four years, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) has pursued research focused on reduction of near-junction thermal resistance through use of diamond substrates and convective and evaporative microfluidics. The options, challenges, and techniques associated with the development of this embedded thermal management technology are described, with emphasis on the accomplishments and status of efforts related to GaN power amplifiers.

Index Terms — Thermal management, near junction, intrachip, GaN, power amplifiers, CVD diamond.

I. INTRODUCTION

As high-power electronic components scale to increasing levels of integration and packaging density, die-level heat dissipation for compound semiconductor devices has been driven above 1 kW/cm², with local hot spots approaching 30 kW/cm², exceeding the limits of the current “remote cooling” paradigm. In conventional cooling architectures for electronics, reliance on thermal conduction and spreading across multiple material interfaces severely constrains the ability of attached coolers with remotely located heat rejection surfaces to prevent excessive chip temperatures, reduce the temperature rise of critical on-chip hot spots, and provide localized cooling for individual chips in a module or in a stack.

As a consequence, reliance on conventional cooling approaches has led to a growing gap between the theoretical capability of advanced semiconductor devices and their thermally-limited performance when operated within a standard system. Notably, even as GaN has emerged as an important platform for microwave/millimeter wave RF power amplifiers (PAs), with demonstrated high electron mobility transistors (HEMTs) with output powers exceeding 40 W/mm [1], the output power of HEMTs in operational systems is today limited to 5-8 W/mm [2], largely due to locally elevated temperatures, as seen in Fig 1. Moreover, continued application of remote cooling has resulted in electronic systems in which the thermal management hardware accounts for a large fraction of the volume, weight, and cost of advanced electronic systems and undermines efforts to transfer emerging electronic components to portable, as well as other small form-factor, applications.

In recognition of these trends, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency Microsystems Technology Office (DARPA-MTO) initiated the Thermal Management Technologies (TMT) program in 2008 to pursue opportunities in the application of micro- and nano-scale thermal science and technology to electronic systems. The Thermal Ground Plane (TGP) thrust developed two-phase high-performance spreaders to replace the copper alloy spreaders in conventional systems. The Microtechnologies for Air Cooled Exchangers (MACE) thrust developed enhanced air-cooled heatsinks with reduced thermal resistance and fan power requirements. The NanoThermal Interfaces (NTI) thrust developed lower thermal resistance thermal interface layers and the Active Cooling Module (ACM) thrust pursued miniature, high-efficiency refrigeration systems, based on thermoelectric or vapor-compression technologies.

These MTO programs demonstrated considerable successes [3] and combined with on-going evolutionary improvements in commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) thermal packaging technology, have drastically improved heat transport and removal after the heat exits the backside of the electronic substrate. However, in many DoD systems, and specifically GaN monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs), the primary thermal bottleneck occurs in a region within 100 μm of the electronic junction, resulting in a very large “near-junction” temperature rise. In this “near-junction” region, often consisting of an epitaxial layer of several microns on a thicker substrate, typically SiC, Si, or sapphire, the local heat

Fig. 1. Demonstrated GaN HEMT operating limit as a function of DC bias based on published data.

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flux substantially exceeds that encountered on the surface of the sun. To address this challenge, the DARPA Near-Junction Thermal Transport (NJTT) program focused on reducing the thermal resistance of the near-junction region of GaN transistors, without negatively affecting the quality of the epitaxy, through the integration of high thermal conductivity diamond substrates [4]. Results to date have demonstrated an increase in the heat density and power handling capability of GaN HEMT devices by greater than 3x [5-10].

The DARPA Intra Chip Embedded Cooling (ICECool) program further develops Generation 3 “embedded cooling” techniques by employing near-junction microfluidics within such high power heat sources and encompasses two thrusts, ICECool Applications (Apps) and ICECool Fundamentals (Fun). Through liquid convection, jet impingement, and evaporation within microchannels in high conductivity substrates, ICECool embedded cooling will be used to remove heat fluxes above 1 kW/cm², with local hot spot fluxes on the order of 5-30 kW/cm², to re-define the state of the art in embedded cooling and overcome thermal limitations and the size, weight, and power (SWaP) bottleneck in next generation electronics.

II. NJTT GAN ON DIAMOND

The material properties of GaN, combined with the relatively high thermal conductivity (350–400 W/mK) of the SiC substrate, has allowed GaN-on-SiC power amplifiers to achieve significantly higher output power, power added efficiency (PAE), and power density than is presently achievable with amplifier circuits based on GaAs or InP. To fully harness the capability of GaN power amplifiers, much greater near-junction thermal enhancement is required to operate at higher output powers and remain within peak junction temperatures limits set by device reliability requirements. Polycrystalline synthetic diamond is an attractive candidate for use as a replacement substrate for high power GaN devices [11], as it offers a thermal conductivity of 2000 W/mK at room temperature, the highest thermal conductivity of any bulk material at room temperature, as well as advantageous electrical and mechanical properties including a high resistance to erosion and corrosion.

The goal of the DARPA NJTT program was to reduce the thermal resistance and demonstrate a 3x improvement in areal power density (W/mm²) of a GaN HEMT without impacting the operational temperature. Approaches considered include high thermal conductivity diamond substrates and microchannel liquid cooling, with the subject of this paper focusing on the accomplishments of teams that developed techniques to transfer the GaN epitaxy to polycrystalline diamond. These techniques included bonding GaN epitaxy to diamond, direct growth of diamond on GaN as a replacement substrate for Si, and growth of diamond in vias within the host SiC substrate.

A. Diamond Substrates

Key technology challenges to successful implementation of GaN on diamond HEMTs include growth of high quality, high thermal conductivity diamond and minimization of the thermal boundary resistance (TBR) between the GaN and diamond. The properties of the nucleation and coalescence region of diamond growth, approximately the first 1 μm of diamond growth, can vary substantially from standard bulk diamond properties. This is less of a concern for approaches that focus on bonding of diamond, as commercially-available polycrystalline diamond substrates are typically grown greater than the intended thickness and the near-interface region is etched away.

Fig. 2. Schematic showing grain coalescence of CVD diamond grown on a HEMT substrate.

Integration approaches that include direct diamond growth on GaN do not permit removal of this low-quality material. Consequently, the growth of polycrystalline or nanocrystalline diamond films directly on the GaN epitaxial layers presents a set of new challenges, in addition to the already complex diamond growth process. Diamond seeding, nucleation, and growth must be accomplished without degrading the host semiconductor. For successful implementation of near-junction cooling, high thermal conductivity diamond must be achieved both in the axial and lateral spreading directions, particularly within the regions nearest the substrate interface and the high heat flux region of the GaN transistor junction. Polycrystalline diamond typically grows as columnar grains, as illustrated in Fig. 2, with small grain size at the nucleation surface that then expands with film thickness. This leads to both anisotropic thermal conductivity, with k in the z direction being initially much greater than k in the lateral direction, and thickness dependent thermal conductivity, with both the axial and lateral thermal conductivity increasing as the diamond becomes thicker [12-15]. As seen in Fig. 3, the room temperature diamond thermal conductivity rapidly increases over the first few microns of growth and approaches a high bulk value that is, nevertheless, dependent on defect and isotopic concentrations within the crystal.

Fig. 3. Room-temperature through-plane thermal conductivity as a function of film thickness for CVD diamond. Adopted with permission from [14].

Minimization of the Thermal Boundary Resistance (TBR) at the interface between the GaN epitaxy and diamond substrate is also crucial for reduction of overall thermal resistance. The TBR encountered in GaN-on-Diamond devices is an aggregate of the near-interface nitride epitaxy, the interface between the nitride and a dielectric nucleation or adhesion promoter (typically <50 nm) dielectric layer, the bulk thermal conductivity of this layer, the interface between the dielectric layer and the polycrystalline diamond, and the spatially varying thermal conductivity of the nucleation and coalescence regions of the diamond thermal substrate. The TBR will be impacted by a variety of factors, including defects, grain boundaries, stoichiometric impurities, disorder in the polycrystalline material and interfacial voids and/or roughness [16-17]. In order for the potential benefits of diamond substrates to be realized, variables within the growth process of the diamond, such as temperature, pressure and hydrogen content, must be carefully selected and controlled while preserving the electrical characteristics of the GaN epitaxial material.

A. Diamond Bonded to GaN

Under NJTT, a team led by BAE Systems investigated use of a low temperature bonding technology to integrate chemical vapor deposition (CVD)-grown polycrystalline diamond within 1 μm of the hot spot of a GaN HEMT while minimizing the impact of GaN/diamond CTE mismatch. This is a “device-first” approach, in which GaN transistors are fabricated and then bonded to the highest thermal conductivity diamond substrates available, eliminating the impact of the diamond nucleation layer on the TBR [5].

GaN HEMT fabrication commences with industry standard GaN-on-SiC epitaxial wafers and is completed using production processes at BAE Systems. Fabricated HEMTs, with a reduced gate pitch for the GaN-on-Diamond device, are then mounted on a temporary carrier wafer and the host

Fig. 4. IR images comparing a GaN-on-SiC (left) to a GaN-on-Diamond (right) transistor, both DC biased at 20 W/mm dissipated power, adopted with permission from [18].

SiC substrate is removed with an etch process designed for low roughness. A bonding adhesive is then deposited on both the GaN surface and a commercially available diamond substrate, and the wafers are bonded at room temperature and subsequently annealed to strengthen the bond [6].

Thermal characterization of the GaN-on-Diamond was completed, with an extracted diamond cross-plane thermal conductivity of 2,160 W/mK and GaN-diamond TBR of 34 $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{GW}$ at room temperature [5-6]. An IR image of a GaN-on-Diamond HEMT and a baseline GaN-on-SiC HEMT DC biased at 20 W/mm dissipation can be seen in Fig. 4, with the GaN-on-Diamond HEMT operating at similar temperatures to the GaN-on-SiC HEMT despite a 3 \times increase in areal power dissipation.

Fig. 5. CW load-pull comparison of 10 GHz input-output power curves for a GaN-on-SiC HEMT vs a GaN-on-Diamond HEMT with 3 \times the periphery in the same device area. Image used with permission from [6].

CW load-pull measurements at 10 GHz were performed on both baseline 4 \times 50 μm GaN-on-SiC HEMTs with 49 μm pitch and 12 \times 50 μm GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs with 19 μm

pitch. The GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs demonstrated an RF output power density of 11 W/mm at 40 V bias, which is the highest RF output power density reported to date for a GaN-on-Diamond HEMT and higher than the baseline, industry standard, GaN-on-SiC HEMT output power of 9 W/mm. As seen in Fig. 5, this equates to 3.6 \times higher RF output power in the same device area as the GaN-on-SiC HEMT while maintaining equivalent junction temperature [6].

B. Diamond Grown on GaN

Two of the NJTT teams, led by Raytheon IDS and TriQuint Semiconductor (now Qorvo) and working with Element Six Technologies, pursued direct growth of microwave plasma CVD (MPCVD) polycrystalline diamond on the GaN after removal of the original host substrate. The process flow commences with an AlGaIn/GaN HEMT structure grown by metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) on a Si (111) substrate. The wafers are mounted on a temporary handle wafer and the host Si substrate as well as the highly defective, low thermal conductivity transition layers are removed. A thin layer of dielectric is deposited onto the exposed GaN epitaxy and MPCVD is used to grow approximately 100 μm of polycrystalline diamond. A TEM image of the epitaxy before and after diamond growth can be seen in Fig. 6. The wafer is then mounted on a carrier wafer for further processing, to correct for wafer bow and maintain compatibility with established industrial fabrication processes [8-9, 19-20].

Fig. 6. TEM cross-section of traditional GaN-on-Si epitaxy and GaN-on-Diamond epitaxy after diamond is grown on GaN. The yellow arrow indicates the thin dielectric layer where diamond growth is initiated. Figure adopted from [21].

Both teams successfully transferred GaN epi to diamond and fabricated and thermally and electrically characterized transistors on large area wafers. The team led by Raytheon fabricated a 3-inch GaN-on-Diamond wafer with a high yield of $10 \times 125 \mu\text{m}$ transistors. The cross-plane diamond thermal conductivity was estimated to be 1481 W/mK and the TBR of the wafer used for transistor fabrication was determined to be 29 $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{GW}$ [10], though on subsequent wafers a TBR between 16 and 21.6 $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{GW}$ was demonstrated [22]. RF load-pull testing at 10 GHz was performed on the GaN-on-Diamond devices and baseline GaN-on-SiC HEMTs, all at 28V operation. The periphery of 1.25 mm was the same for both GaN-on-SiC and GaN-on-Diamond transistors. The

GaN-on-SiC gate spacing was 40 μm whereas the GaN-on-Diamond gate spacing was 10 μm , to take advantage of the enhanced thermal conductivity of the diamond substrate. The measured GaN-on-Diamond HEMT RF output power was 5 W/mm, demonstrating a 3.7 \times improvement in areal power density over the GaN-on-SiC baseline [23].

Fig. 7. CW load-pull results of a $2 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ 10 GHz GaN-on-Diamond HEMT biased at 40V, with an RF output power density of 7.4 W/mm at peak PAE. Figure used with permission from [7].

The team led by TriQuint Semiconductor (Qorvo) also demonstrated device quality GaN-on-Diamond epitaxy and completed detailed characterization of fabricated HEMTs within NJTT. The TBR at the GaN and diamond interface, measured by micro-Raman, was 18 $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{GW}$. RF load-pull measurements of a $2 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ GaN-on-Diamond HEMT were completed at 10 GHz and several drain voltages, with a maximum of 7.4 W/mm output power at 40 V bias, as seen in Fig. 7. It was also determined that, for the same power dissipation, the GaN-on-Diamond HEMT had 25–30% lower temperature rise than that of a GaN-on-SiC HEMT with the same dimensions. At that time, this was a record for GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs and was comparable to the output power of standard GaN-on-SiC HEMTs, despite the GaN being sourced from Si [7-8].

Element Six Technologies separately pursued device reliability tests of GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs created through MPCVD growth of diamond on GaN. They were able to demonstrate continuous operation of GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs with channel temperatures of 350 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3,000+ hours, as compared to baseline GaN-on-Si HEMTs that catastrophically failed at those temperatures [24]. Element Six has also demonstrated operation of GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs for over 175,000 device-hours [25].

C. Diamond Grown in Vias

An alternative approach to integrating GaN with CVD diamond, explored by a team led by Northrop Grumman AS, is direct growth of diamond in vias etched into the SiC substrate of a standard GaN-on-SiC HEMT. In this approach, diamond is selectively grown in the thermal vias, minimizing

wafer bow and stress for device fabrication. Unique to this approach is that the low-loss SiC substrate is not modified underneath any passive network structures that may be necessary for a power amplifier.

The process begins with an industry standard GaN-on-SiC HEMT. Backside vias are etched into the SiC substrate, aligned to where the transistor regions will be. The wafer is then seeded with nano-diamond particles and a thin, conformal, nucleation layer is grown. The backside diamond is then etched from all regions except the thermal vias and an additional CVD diamond deposition is completed to further fill the thermal vias [26], with a projected $3.1\times$ improvement in RF output power per unit area while maintaining similar junction temperatures as the baseline GaN-on-SiC HEMT. Through effort within NJTT, a process to deposit diamond within thermal vias was developed, with future electrical and thermal characterization the subject of the DARPA ICECool and the DARPA Diamond Round Robin programs.

III. ICECOOL PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Embedded cooling represents a third generation (Gen-3) thermal management technology for electronic circuits, following on the Gen-1 air conditioning approaches of the early years of the Information Age (~1950-1970) and the subsequent decades-long commitment to the Gen-2 attached cooler paradigm. The scientific and engineering foundation for the aggressive implementation of embedded cooling has been driven by some 30 years of thermofluid R&D, initiated by the publication of the Tuckerman & Pease microchannel cooler paper in 1981 [27] and more recently by compact heat exchanger and biofluidic applications. Nevertheless substantial development and modeling challenges must be overcome to achieve full implementation of the Gen-3 embedded cooling technology.

Fig. 8. Conceptual ICECool device.

NJTT demonstrated the disruptive capability of GaN-on-Diamond HEMTs and opened the door for power amplifiers with minimal thermal restrictions. The DARPA ICECool program further extends the “Gen-3” embedded cooling technology thrust to revolutionize thermal technology and

enable the performance required by next generation electronic systems. Thus, ICECool involves the integration of thermal substrates and interconnects, using high thermal conductivity—as well as thermoelectric—materials to link on-chip hot spots to convectively and evaporatively cooled microchannels. Such intrachip enhanced cooling approaches are being designed to be compatible with the materials, fabrication procedures, and thermal management needs of emerging homogeneous and heterogeneous integration in 3D chip stacks, 2.5D constructs, and planar arrays. A conceptual ICECool device is shown in Fig. 8.

The ICECool Applications thrust encompasses an embedded high performance computing thrust and GaN MMIC thrust, which will be the focus of this section. ICECool Applications Phase II will culminate with a demonstration of functional GaN MMICs with a greater than $3\times$ improvement in RF output power while maintaining reliable peak junction temperatures. The ICECool Fundamentals thrust is investigating the introduction of evaporative microfluidic structures and highly efficient two-phase cooling into substrates, including SiC and diamond, and is intended to develop phase-change thermofluidic building blocks for next generation electronics.

A. ICECool High Performance GaN

Embedded cooling approaches explored within ICECool Applications for GaN power amplifiers include microfluidic cooling of two substrate categories: GaN-on-Diamond and GaN-on-SiC. The GaN-on-Diamond work, led by Raytheon IDS, Northrop Grumman AS, and BAE Systems, is extending the work begun under NJTT from transistor demonstrations to MMIC demonstrations and incorporating the benefits of active microfluidic cooling with the passive cooling enhancement from GaN-on-Diamond. The GaN-on-SiC with microfluidic cooling efforts are being led by Lockheed Martin, Boeing, and Nuvotronics, with the intended goal of near-term insertion in

Fig. 9. On the left, a schematic of an ICECool approach with a GaN-on-diamond epitaxy and diamond microchannels. On the right, an SEM image of high-aspect ratio GaN-on-diamond microchannels, adopted from [22].

next generation electronic systems.

In one ICECool project, a team led by Raytheon IDS and including Element Six Technologies is developing GaN-on-Diamond MMICs with diamond micro-channels, engineered to bring convective heat removal close to the device junction, with completed analysis indicating the approach will achieve a die-level dissipation of 1.23 kW/cm^2 with transistor hot spot dissipation of 38 kW/cm^2 . Key focus areas of this effort are

micro-fabrication of high aspect ratio diamond microchannels, low thermal resistance hermetic bonding of Si and MPCVD diamond, and thermal/electrical co-design to maximize MMIC power density, efficiency and RF performance. The team has further developed the diamond grown on GaN work described in Sec. IIB and increased the thickness of the diamond by 3× without affecting the electrical properties. As seen in Fig. 9, a high power, high selectivity etch process has been successfully developed to create high quality microchannels

Fig. 10. On the left, an illustration of a GaN-on-SiC HEMT with diamond-line thermal via's with jet impingement cooling. On the right, an SEM image of CVD diamond grown in a thermal via, adopted with permission from [28].

etched in the diamond [22].

A team led by Northrop Grumman AS is developing high-flow impingement jet cooling of a GaN-on-SiC power amplifier with diamond-lined microchannels. As seen in Fig. 10, this work merges the diamond via growth approach developed in NJTT with impingement jet cooling. The near-junction diamond lined channels spreads the heat near the HEMT hot spot and transfers it to the incoming fluid, enabling heat dissipation of 1 kW/cm² at the die level and 30 kW/cm² at the MMIC level. With the thermal performance enabled by ICECool, the team projects a 4× improvement in MMIC output power and a 6× improvement in MMIC heat flux [28-29]. Measurements of the thermal prototype are now in-progress and design and demonstration of a fully functional power amplifier have begun.

The team led by Lockheed Martin took the alternative approach of using a GaN-on-SiC power amplifier device with minor modifications to the backside substrate, which consisted of etching an array of pins into the SiC substrate, and attaching the die to a microfabricated manifold to bring the coolant to the back surface of the die. This approach is also readily compatible with die designs that do not utilize the substrate backside enhancements. The designed palladium manifold is created using an additive, photolithographic deposition process that enables high design flexibility and complex internal microfluidic routing networks [30]. A GaN-on-SiC thermal prototype die containing etched pins on the substrate, resistor heaters, and HEMTs, was attached to the palladium manifold and flow tested. A schematic of the microfabricated manifold, an optical image of the thermal

Fig. 11. On the left, a schematic of the palladium manifold used for microfluidic cooling of a GaN-on-SiC HEMT. In the middle, an IR image of an ICECool thermal prototype under test, with 1 kW/cm² die-level heat flux and 30 kW/cm² transistor-level heat flux. On the right, an optical image of a fabricated thermal prototype, adopted with permission from [31].

prototype, and an IR image of the thermal prototype under test are shown in Fig. 11.

Thermal measurements demonstrated a die-level heat flux of 1.1 kW/cm² and HEMT-level heat flux of 30 kW/cm², using 40% propylene glycol, 60% water, as the coolant at a flow rate of 120 mL/min [31]. The measured junction temperature was well below the temperature required for reliable GaN HEMT operation and, in conjunction with the dissipated heat fluxes, the program met the Phase I goals of ICECool Applications. Work is now on-going to extend this demonstration to GaN MMICs, for a projected 3× improvement in output power.

B. Thermal-Mechanical-Electrical Co-Design

Establishment of true thermal-mechanical-electrical co-design remains a key barrier to making embedded cooling a reality for next generation electronic chips. In the ICECool program thermal-mechanical-electrical co-design techniques are being developed that move progressively from passive, thermally-informed designs, which recognize the impact of temperature on functional performance, to active thermal co-design, which places functional paths and blocks in the most favorable locations on the chip, to fully-integrated thermal-mechanical-electrical co-design, which deals with the impact of microfluidic channels and thermal substrates/interconnects on the mechanical and electrical design and informs the placement of electrical devices and cells, and interactively balances the use of resources to optimize layout for energy consumption, functional performance, and mechanical stability.

The ICECool co-design effort is attempting to create a new class of thermal-mechanical-electrical design tools necessary for implementation of embedded cooling. These tools are being developed on top of existing multi-physics and CAD tools such that upon completion of the ICECool program they will be accessible to the broader design community [32].

II. CONCLUSION

Recent efforts funded by DARPA-MTO, specifically within the TMT, NJTT and ICECool programs, are establishing a new paradigm in embedded cooling of GaN power amplifiers. Accomplishments in the NJTT program were reviewed, including demonstration of $3\times$ the power handling capability in a GaN-on-Diamond HEMT compared to an industry-standard GaN-on-SiC HEMT. An overview and status of efforts within the DARPA ICECool program was given, with an emphasis placed on the efforts related to GaN power amplifiers.

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